

RECIPROcity

D.1.4

Mapping & Impact Assessment Report

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Publishable summary

The first two sections of this report discuss the process and principles followed for selecting use cases for replication as called for RECIPROCITY project definition and Grant Agreement. Definitions of Lighthouse and Follower cities, and pertinent characteristics of replication use cases are presented, together with various earlier European efforts for smart and clean mobility and impact assessment, including Tide, Flow, Trilater and SHOW impact assessment approaches. The CIVITAS initiative has provided a fundamental framework for the RECIPROCITY project, and it has been adopted as the source of the guiding principles for impact assessment.

The third section of the report presents a summary of the preliminary work on simulation-based assessment of the environmental impact and passenger transport effectiveness performed on two mobility use-cases: “32. Intelligent BRT” (Istanbul, TR) and “6. SOftly MObile Tourism Mobility” (Alpine Pearls/Werfenweng, AT). The PTV Vissim tool¹ was used for simulation. Specifically, CO₂ emission and passenger experience parameters of two lines (Avcılar – Zincirlikuyu, Zincirlikuyu – Söğütlüçeşme) of the Istanbul Metropolitan BRT system and three lines of the Werfenweng W3 Shuttle (Werfenweng-Pfarrwerfen-Bischofshofen, Werfenweng-Pfarrwerfen-Werfen and Tenneck-Werfen) were evaluated under various scenarios. For the Intelligent BRT use-case, it is shown that autonomous platooning significantly enhances transport effectiveness, decreasing passenger delays while reducing fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions by up to 21%.

For the SOftly Mobile Tourism Mobility use case, it is shown that e-cars and e-bikes improve passenger experience, in terms of reduced waiting times, while also significantly reducing local emissions. An important issue, however, is that indirect emissions from e-vehicles, that is greenhouse gases generated in energy production plants, can reach significant levels, even though not local.

In the concluding section of the report, connections of and interactions between T 1.4 Mapping and Impact Assessment and T 1.5 Replication Roadmap Definition activities of RECIPROCITY are reviewed, pointing out the next steps to be taken in the following stages of the Project.

¹ <https://www.ptvgroup.com/en/solutions/products/ptv-vissim/>)

List of abbreviations

BRT	Bus Rapid Transit
DLL	Dynamic Link Library
EC	European Commission
LMW	Local Mobility Workshop
MMW	Master Mobility Workshop
MTF	Mobility Task Force
PHEM	Passenger car and Heavy duty vehicle Emissions Model
PTV	Planung Transport Verkehr AG in Karlsruhe, Germany.
RCP	RECIPROCITY
RRDW	Replication Roadmap Definition Workshop
VISSIM	"Verkehr In Städten - SIM ulationsmodell" (German for "Traffic in cities - simulation model")

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1. Introduction

RECIPROCITY will create a replication ecosystem of more than 20 cities and municipalities that vary in size, requirements, and level of mobility advancement. These cities will then be engaged in support activities to accelerate the replication and scaling up of the outcomes of demonstration and pilot mobility projects. These activities include matchmaking, capacity-building, training, finance, and legal support, as well as knowledge sharing and exchange.

The first work package, IDENTIFY, focused on collect information on mobility needs, requirements, and existing innovative mobility solutions. In that context, identification and consultation of relevant stakeholders and citizen groups and conduct a thorough mapping of best practices was a key point during this work package. Work on the T.1.4 took place at the beginning of the dissemination of WP1 and aimed at doing the link between the first tasks and the last tasks of this WP, especially the work of the T.1.3.

RECIPROCITY will create a replication ecosystem of more than 20 cities and municipalities that vary in size, requirements, and level of mobility advancement. These cities will then be engaged in support activities to accelerate the replication and scaling up of the outcomes of demonstration and pilot mobility projects. These activities include matchmaking, capacity-building, training, finance, and legal support, as well as knowledge sharing and exchange.

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To enrich the exchanges that took place during the Mobility Workshops (T1.3) and, more generally speaking, to highlight the opportunities and possibilities of existing innovative mobility solutions, a mapping and impact assessment of mobility case studies was created.

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In this report, we will first examine the methodology used to create the mapping and impact assessment tool (final summary of the case study selection). Then, we will review the results obtained (final summary of impact assessment). Finally, we will examine how the results obtained can be used for the T.1.5 work.

2. Final summary of the use-case study selection

As a reminder, per the grant agreement, the T.1.4 work was divided into 4 parts:

I. Identification: Relevant mobility case studies will be systematically collected, particularly those generated in EIP-SSC and other smart city initiatives and those innovations from the lighthouse cities within the RECIPROCITY ecosystem. Two further key resources that will be consulted for the mapping will be the case study selection by Eltis (www.eltis.org) and CIVITAS (www.civitas.eu).

II. Analysis & prioritization: The selected case studies from step 1) will be assessed and ranked based on their impact using the guidelines set out by the EC . We will assess the technology dimension (e.g. interoperability), the political institutional dimension (e.g. ecosystem, need to change the regulations), the social-cultural dimension (e.g. social acceptance, gender equality, inclusion) and the economic/business dimension (e.g. business model).

III. Feasibility assessment: We will examine the feasibility of these solutions by providing simulation-based impact assessment for replication led by OKAN. These simulations will employ information models gathering territorial data from each region in the ecosystem to simulate performances and impacts, to compare scenarios, to manage risks and to share projects with stakeholders while ensuring data protection.

IV. Project selection: A subset of suitable innovative mobility solutions will be chosen based on step 2) and 3) and will be processed for the employment in the workshop in T1.5.

It is important at that point to explain why we chose to use the term “use-case selection” instead of the term “case-study”. For us, a case study can be defined “as an intensive study about a person, a group of people or a unit, which is aimed to generalize over several units².”.

² <https://ebn.bmj.com/content/21/1/7>

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We chose to add the term “use-case” because our study is based on use-cases generated in the RECIPROCITY ecosystem and is aimed to generalize over several units within the RECIPROCITY ecosystem. At the same time, one needs to understand that the work of the T.1.4 focused on cases from the CIVITAS and the use-cases generated within the RECIPROCITY ecosystem while the work of the T.1.5 will focus on the use-cases generated within the RECIPROCITY ecosystem.

So, the use-case study selection was in the heart of the T.1.4 work, meaning that it was an essential element for achieving the T.1.5 work. The grant agreement gave some basis for this work:

- Number of cases to select.
- Sources to check to select these cases
- Guidelines to follow
- Dimensions to assess

At the same time, some questions were still to be answered:

- Number of cases really needed to go on with the project (replication workshops, training sessions...). How should we define a “subset of suitable innovative mobility solutions?” We had to define the needs for other tasks to get that definition
 - Difference between lighthouse cities and follower cities
 - Quality of the real-life sources – in addition to the use-case summaries that could be found online, we had to work with real-life use-cases, meaning that we needed to be precise about the information needed from stakeholders to go on with our work
 - Definition of “suitable innovative mobility solutions”
-
- **Number of cases**

There was some debate between the T.1.4 group as to determine the number of cases that would be needed to go on with the project. Two options were considered:

- Getting as much use cases as every partner could to use the cases to build the model.
- Staying in line with the grant agreement and only work with two use-cases

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At the end, an option somewhere between the two options was chosen. We chose to start with trying to build the model, determine what the inputs needed and pick up the number of use-cases needed after that step. It was felt that the use-cases would not be needed until the replication workshops, allowing us a little more time to get them through the process of the local mobility workshops (June & July 2021) and not before that.

- **Difference between lighthouse and follower cities**

The definition of lighthouse and follower cities was worked on when the grant agreement was written. As this definition was needed to go through the work of the T.1.4, the project group decided to suggest one to the whole consortium.

After some discussion inside the group, some key points were considered:

- Cities could **be both** lighthouse and follower cities at the same time, depending on their needs and requirements in different topics
- As the RCP project aims at providing solutions **for cities,** we should propose definitions to cities in the first workshops and let them work on them, to make sure that we jibe with their reality
- These two definitions are suggestions for the RCP project in order to offer the best activities and training to cities. They are not definitive labels and there is no pejorative connotation to the « follower cities » expression.

The criteria to distinguish lighthouse and follower cities was designed as below :

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Table 1 : Definition of lighthouse and follower cities

Lighthouse Cities	Follower cities
Are willing to share to other cities how they succeed – ideally, they have participated to mobility projects for the exchange of best practices (such as European missions)	Are committed to implement some changes in the automotive and the mobility sectors
Are willing to lead and disseminate – for example, they have demonstration areas or are ready to launch some	Are willing to share their needs, challenges and pain points in terms of "transformation" to (partly) smart cities to other cities and stakeholders
Have implemented some changes in the automotive & mobility sectors – they may have gotten a Mobility-related award or have public recognition for that	Are willing to replicate the RCP projects and have the means to do so and are willing to develop a roadmap with concrete projects linked to their mobility strategy.
Are able to go through a monitoring of their performances as lighthouse cities, including the projects that they have implemented in the past	Are willing to share some data & information on their project, even with non-partners of the RCP project and are willing to comply with performance monitoring, even after the end of the project

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- **Quality of real-life sources**

An issue that arised soon in the process of working on the task was the issue of the quality of real-life sources. We had to get some use-cases from stakeholders, as per the grant agreement. That led to two issues:

- The stakeholders who could provide use-cases for the RECIPROCITY project were the stakeholders already involved in the project, meaning that it would cause some limitations to the thematic of the use-cases that we could work with. As opposed to what was done when working with the CIVITAS use-cases, where we could pick in a database the subjects that we felt pertinent to work with, in real-life, if the stakeholders were not willing to share use-cases on a specific topic, then it would not be possible to tackle this subject.
- The stakeholders had limited time to work on the use-cases, i.e we had to find a way to quickly get the information, meaning that we had to be precise about what were the inputs needed in order to make the model work.
- **Definition of “suitable innovative mobility solutions”**

As cliché as it may sound, RECIPROCITY’s stakeholders come from different countries all over Europe, have different backgrounds, different means and different needs and requirements. It meant that what a stakeholder from a country A would call an “innovative mobility solution” might not be an “innovative mobility solution” for a stakeholder from a country B.

So, it was impossible, for both the T.1.4 work and both the project, to find a general definition of a “suitable innovative mobility solution” and it would not have made so much sense either.

After some discussion, it was decided to give the final say to stakeholders as to define a “suitable innovative mobility solution”. The Mobility Task Forces would give some feedback on the potential for replication in the regions to help the stakeholders find the most suitable innovative mobility solutions for their needs during the replication workshops.

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2.1. Creation of the impact assessment model

The impact assessment was thought as a tool for RECIPROCITY's stakeholders to assist them in the process between getting evidence and taking a decision. The final objective of the project is to ensure the replication of 20 innovative projects, meaning that as a consortium, we had to give stakeholders every tool needed to support them during this process.

Questions asked before starting to build the model

- What are the inputs? How will they be obtained?
- How will the received data be processed?
- What kind of outputs will be generated and how?
- How will the validity of the produced outputs be evaluated?

Method suggestions

Several methods were considered when building the impact model assessment. We will discuss the main characteristics of them in order to explain the final decision taken regarding the method used.

1. Tide impact assessment

Key characteristics of the TIDE assessment method:

- It is intended for municipalities to assess the impact of a measure on society as a whole (economic, social and environmental impacts).
- It combines quantified and qualitative effects into an overall performance score.
- It is primarily intended for ex-ante assessments, but also applicable ex-post.
- It can include economic viability indicators (data allowing).
- It can be applied to urban transport measures with different impacts and scales (investment, area affected, etc.).
- It is not intended to displace more sophisticated assessments usually applied to large-scale projects.
- It makes it possible to visualize all impacts.

2. Flow impact assessment

The offered FLOW assessment procedure gives the cities the possibility to evaluate a wide range of effects across multiple disciplines –both in a **quantitative** and **qualitative** manner. The developed tool is able to cover the **environmental**, **social** and **economic** aspects, but also the impacts on the **transport network performance**. The developed tool is applicable to both ex-ante assessments and ex-post evaluations of all kinds of walking and cycling measures.

Prior to the application of the tool, one has to be familiar with the various steps of the appraisal procedure. A typical workflow of the overall assessment methodology is divided into six steps.

Aggregation of indicators:

- Multi-criteria analysis (MCA)
- Weighted benefit analysis (WBA)
- Cost-benefit analysis (CBA)
- Qualitative appraisal (only as add-on to CBA)

3. Trilateral impact assessment

Nine basic impact mechanisms were formulated for **automation studies**. The purpose of these mechanisms is to ensure that the assessment covers systematically the **intended** and **unintended**, direct and indirect, short-term and long-term impacts of both automated vehicle users and non-users. It is recommended that these mechanisms be used for all impact areas of automated driving studies.

1. Direct modification of the driving task, drive behaviour or travel experience
2. Direct influence by physical and/or digital infrastructure
3. Indirect modification of automated vehicle user behaviour
4. Indirect modification of non-user behaviour
5. Modification of interaction between automated vehicles and other road-users
6. Modification of exposure / amount of travel
7. Modification of modal choice

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8.Modification of route choice

9.Modification of consequences due to different vehicle design

So, in theory the impact evaluation of a measure is very easy:

- A **set of indicators** that describe the important characteristics of the situation is proposed,
- We observe the value of these indicators **before and after** the implementation of the measure,
- While **preventing other elements from influencing** the indicators or removing the impact of the other elements before assessing the “after” situation,
- Then we **compare** before and after situation and finally we **draw conclusions** about the impacts induced by this specific measure.

However in practice many elements can make impact evaluation difficult and even impossible, especially in a real, complex urban environment. For this reason it was important to agree on an evaluation approach that is both highly qualitative and practically applicable in each CIVITAS city.

4. Final method: the SHOW impact assessment method

The overall SHOW eco-system impact assessment framework will include KPIs as calculated from the in-depth analyses from the different impact areas, and potentially non-processed KPIs collected from demonstration sites and simulations. As such, the overall impact analysis brings together the analyses done in the different activities of WP1 and especially for the T.1.4.

- A13.1: Road safety
- A13.2: Traffic efficiency, energy, and environmental impact
- A13.3: Societal, employability and equality
- A13.4: Urban logistics
- A13.5: User experience, awareness and acceptance

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CIVITAS Initiative which is a European action that supports cities in the implementation of an integrated sustainable, clean and energy efficient transport policy, proposes the following points as important drivers for the initiation, as well as for an efficient and successful implementation of mobility management measures : (CIVITAS, 2012)

- Senior level political interest is necessary in order to make principle decisions at an early stage of the project ;
- The competence and engagement of the project team and good cooperation between all local partners as well as all stakeholders involved (e.g. public transport operator, site owners, representative of the target group), is necessary ;
- It is advisable to appoint a full-time mobility manager who is responsible for the overall coordination of the measures and who works on this issue on a day-to-day basis ;
- A good communication strategy, including local media providing informative and personal description of the measure, supports the implementation process. Whenever possible, an independent facilitator should be engaged, e.g. for meetings or workshops ;
- The availability of good framework conditions (access management, suitable bike network, existing car-sharing or car-pooling services and high quality public transport system) enables the target group to be offered real alternatives to the individual motorised transport mode ;
- For the development of area-wide mobility plans it is advisable to use commuter plans at company level as a basis ;
- Exchange of experiences with other municipalities, which have already achieved positive effects with the help of such measures.

In the selection, within the scope of Task T 1.5, of use cases to be replicated, these drivers will also be fully taken into consideration.

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5. Selection of use-cases

Based on the indicators discussed above, we started to examine the CIVITAS data base to find use-cases that would be relevant to test the impact assessment model built.

10 CIVITAS use-cases were considered for this work:

	UC 1.1	UC 1.2	UC 1.3	UC 1.4	UC 1.5	UC 1.6	UC 1.7	UC 1.8	UC 1.9	UC 1.10	UC 2.1	UC 2.2	UC 3.1	UC 3.2	UC 3.3	UC 3.4	UC 3.5
Mega Demonstration Sites																	
Rouen site	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x			x				x
Rennes site	x		x	x						x		x					
Linköping site	x		x			x	x						x	x			x
Kista site	x	x	x			x	x										x
Madrid site	x	x	x			x	x	x		x						x	x
Graz site		x	x														x
Salzburg site		x	x		x	x								x			
Carinthia site	x					x						x					
Karlsruhe site	x	x				x	x		x			x	x				
Aachen site	x			x		x				x							x*
Braunschweig site	x					x		x									
Implementation score	82%	55%	64%	27%	18%	82%	45%	18%	9%	36%	9%	27%	27%	9%	9%	45%	9%

Table 2: Overview of use cases in focus at each site (SHOW).

In line with the method agreed, some criteria to study the use-cases were defined:

UC1.1 : Automated passengers/cargo mobility in Cities under normal traffic & environmental conditions.

Includes normal speeds, normal/smooth traffic context, no traffic or other environmental complexity. Indicatively: dedicated lane, pre-defined more or less routes, no roundabouts or short curves, no need for self-change of lane, no heavy traffic, no extreme weather conditions (e.g., snow or heavy rain).

UC1.2 : Automated passengers/cargo mobility in Cities under complex traffic & environmental conditions

Includes normal speeds, complex traffic or environmental context (e.g., curvatures in roundabouts, etc.), when any of the above (UC1.1) restrictions is applied (e.g., heavy traffic, extreme weather conditions, etc.).

UC1.3 : Interfacing non automated vehicles and travelers (including VRUs)

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According to the Drive2theFuture project, to achieve a VRU redefinition towards Autonomous Vehicles (AV) per transport mode and AV level it is essential to take stock of current definitions and underlying concepts.

UC1.4 : Energy sustainable automated passengers/cargo mobility in Cities

Solutions (e.g., inductive dynamic or static charging, RES based charging, etc.) that make the service sustainable, i.e., able to cover the same service with the electric AV. (area, frequency, cost) as with the conventional one.

UC2.1 : Automated mixed spatial mobility

Mixed mobility of cargo/passengers at the same time within the same vehicle, but at different parts of the vehicle or with towed vehicle. Separation and security of cargo compartments, as well as access to it and combined passenger/cargo loading/unloading will be demonstrated.

UC2.2: Automated mixed temporal mobility

Same vehicle used at different times for passenger and cargo transfer (e.g., in the morning for travelling people and in the night for goods supply to shops).

With these objectives in mind, and in addition to the grant agreement's obligations, we selected three RECIPROCITY use-cases identified in the T1.3 interviews and in the Local Mobility Workshops, to work with to test the model before finally testing it with real-life use-cases. We will discuss the simulation-based impact assessment carried out with those two use cases in the following part of this report.

3. Use Cases Being Studied

This section presents the brief descriptions of the use cases considered for this study, as they are presented in the RECIPROCITY use cases database (Annex I).

3.1. Intelligent BRT (Istanbul Metrobus, TR)

The aims of this use-case are listed as: “Reducing general road traffic; carrying high volume passenger traffic on reserved/dedicated BRT routes; reducing waiting time and trip duration by intelligent and autonomous BRT management - highly reduced inter-vehicle gap; reducing CO₂ emission by intelligent and autonomous BRT management.”

Istanbul BRT (Figure 1) has been operational since 2007. The two lines considered in the present study have been operating in the traditional, non-autonomous fashion, referred as Base Scenario in the simulations reported below, since 2008 (Avcılar-Zincilikuyu, Line 34, 29km, 27 stations) and 2009 (Zincirlikuyu-Söğütlüçeşme, Line 34Z, 11km, 8 stations), respectively (Figure 2).

As the 40 km combined path of the two lines does not have more than 50m of altitude difference between any two points, only two-dimensional model of the topology has been used, without any elevation consideration in the simulation.

Figure 1: Istanbul BRT (Source: <https://cdn.karar.com/news/1318721.jpg>)

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Figure 2: Istanbul BRT Map

The number of trips on these lines is given in Table 3. Passenger load distribution over stations and over time-of-day are given in Figures 3 and 4, respectively.

Table 3: Number of trips per BTR line (**emphasis** on lines considered in simulation)

Line	Max trips/hr	Daily trips
34	85	1091
34A	52	326
34T	23	170
34Z	27	585
34G	5	62

Figure 3: Passenger demand distribution by stations – Average, January – April 2011 (Source: KARSAN – OKAN, 2011)

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Figure 4: Passenger demand distribution by time of day, Average, January – June 2011 (ibid.)

3.1.1. Intelligent BRT scenarios

While the base scenarios, B1 and B2, considered for simulation are traditional driver-centered scenarios, the autonomous scenarios A1 through A5 aim at intelligent and autonomous platooning.

Figure 5: BRT Platooning (ibid.)

Characteristics of the simulated scenarios are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: BRT Scenario Configurations

Scenario	Desired Speed (km/h)	Departure Time Difference (s)	Desired Acceleration (m/s ²)	Desired Deceleration (m/s ²)
B1: driver, no platooning	70	-	0.5	1.5
B2: driver, platooning	70	10	0.5	1.5
A1: Autonomous	70	3	0.6	1.8
A2: Autonomous	90	3	0.6	1.8
A3: Autonomous	90	10	0.6	1.8
A4: Autonomous	70	10	0.6	1.8
A5: Autonomous	90	10	0.8	2

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Bus characteristics are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: BRT Bus Characteristics

<i>Model</i>	<i>CapaCity (Mercedes-Benz)</i>
<i>Length</i>	<i>19m</i>
<i>Weight (empty/max)</i>	<i>18.5/32 Tons</i>
<i>No. of doors</i>	<i>3</i>
<i>Capacity</i>	<i>160</i>
<i>Fuel</i>	<i>Diesel</i>
<i>Emission Class</i>	<i>Euro III</i>

3.2. SOftly MOBile Tourism Mobility (Alpine Pearls / Werfenweng, AT)

Softly Mobile Holiday in Werfenweng (Austria): SOftly MOBile guests come to Werfenweng by train and not by car. Upon arrival at Bischofshofen train station, a pickup service is ready to take passengers directly to their lodging. Round the clock mobility is the motto at this Alpine Pearl and this is taken seriously. A fleet of climate-friendly vehicles are offered to passengers, including pedal/electric-powered bicycles (PedElecs), e-mountain bikes, e-cars etc³.

The shuttle, rental e-cars and e-bikes are shown in Figures 6 through 8, respectively. The data used in the simulations were obtained by direct communications with Alpine Pearls officials in August 2021.

The shuttle line simulated in this study was (Figure 9): Tenneck-Werfen-Pfarrwerfen-Werfenweng. Altitude cross section of this shuttle route is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 6: Alpine Pearls shuttle, Werfenweng³ (© Alpine Pearls/Dietmar Denger)

Figure 7: Alpine Pearls e-cars for rental , Werfenweng³ (© Alpine Pearls/Dietmar Denger)

³ <https://www.alpine-pearls.com/en/holiday-destinations/austria/werfenweng>

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Figure 8: Alpine Pearls e-bike, Werfenweng (© Alpine Pearls/Dietmar Denger)

Figure 9: Aerial view of the Tenneck-Werfen-Pfarrwerfen-Werfenweng shuttle line (Yellow-Red-Violet)

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Figure 10: Aerial view of the simulated line with altitude cross section.

Together with this shuttle line, 20 mountain e-bikes are available for rental, and year-round e-car sharing with 11 cars (9 BMWi3, 1 Renault Zoe, 1 ESmart) is available.

E-cars are assumed to share shuttle routes, but they also travel on other roads. So only a percentage of e-car travel loads shuttle routes. This percentage is a parameter for different simulation scenarios.

E-bikes travel only on designated bike routes, so they do not share roads with shuttles or e-cars. Based on the number of bikers, travelled distance and route topology, energy expenditures are estimated.

For e-cars and shuttles, passenger transport statistics as well as energy expenditure, as well as CO₂ emissions, in case of shuttles, are evaluated for different traffic load and mix scenarios.

The certified energy characteristics of e-bikes and e-cars as published in (Weiss, et.al., 2020) have been used in the work reported below.

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3.2.1. Softly Mobile Tourism mobility (Werfenweng) scenarios

The shuttle is modelled in PTV Vissim tool as shown in Figure 12. It is taken as a van with empty weight between 1940 – 2060 kg, speed up to 50 km/h, and a capacity of 20 passengers.

Figure 11: PTV Vissim model of the Shuttle vehicle in the SOftly MObile Tourism Mobility (Werfenweng) Simulation

The simulation model for the e-cars used in Werfenweng is shown in Figure 13. Empty weight is taken as 800 kg.

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Figure 12: Werfenweng e-car simulation model

For shuttle and e-car dynamics, acceleration/deceleration characteristics were set as presented in Table 7. Maximum speeds of 50 m/h are assumed in the Werfenweng region.

Table 7: Desired Acceleration Deceleration (m/s^2) of Diesel Shuttles

Speed (km/h)	Acc	Acc _{min}	Acc _{max}	Speed (km/h)	Dec	Dec _{max}	Dec _{min}
0	3,75	2,45	4,375	0	-2,75	-3	-2,55
10	3,375	1,86625	4,375	10	-2,75	-3	-2,55
20	2,8575	1,625	4,375	20	-2,75	-3	-2,55
30	2,46	1,44	4,375	30	-2,75	-3	-2,55
40	2,125	1,28375	4,375	40	-2,75	-3	-2,55
50	1,83	1,14625	4,09125	50	-2,75	-3	-2,55

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Table 8: Certified e-bike characteristics (Source: Weiss, et.al., 2020)

Mass (kg):	98
Power (kW):	0,29
Battery capacity (kWh):	0,47
Certified energy consumption (kWh/100 km):	0,54
Real-world energy consumption (kWh/100 km):	0,71
Indirect CO ₂ emissions—certified energy consumption (g CO ₂ /km):	1,6
Indirect CO ₂ emissions—real-world energy consumption (g CO ₂ /km):	2,1

Table 9: Certified e-Car characteristics (ibid.)

Mass (kg) (211)	1689
Power (kW) (218)	150
Battery capacity (kWh) (216)	46
Certified energy consumption (kWh/100 km) (206)	16,0
Real-world energy consumption (kWh/100 km) (179)	18,4
Indirect CO ₂ emissions—certified energy consumption (g CO ₂ /km) (206)	47
Indirect CO ₂ emissions—real-world energy consumption (g CO ₂ /km) (179)	54

In the simulation results reported below, the passenger distribution presented in Table 8 is taken into account. Passenger demand and vehicle operation are considered only from 08:00 AM to 08:00 PM, that is, a 12 hr period, daily.

Further elaboration on days of the week, night hours, and especially seasonal variations may also be studied. In the present report, as the aim is only to demonstrate the viability of the simulation tool for impact assessment, a single day is taken as representative.

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Table 10: Werfenweng passenger distribution

Station	PAX/hr	PAX/day
Tenneck:	10	120
Werfen:	22	264
Praffwerfen:	16	192
Werfenweng:	12	144
TOTAL:	60	720

3.3. The simulation tool PTV Vissim

PTV Vissim⁴ is a microscopic multi-modal traffic flow simulation tool, supplied by PTV Group⁵.

“Whether comparing junction geometries, analysing public transport priority schemes or considering the effects of certain signalling – PTV Vissim allows you to simulate traffic patterns exactly. Motorised private transport, goods transport, rail and road related public transport, pedestrians and cyclists. PTV Vissim displays all road users and their interactions in one model. Scientifically sound motion models provide a realistic modelling of all road users. As PTV Vissim is multi-modal it is possible to simulate the interactions between motorised traffic and other road users such as pedestrians and cyclists, meaning accurate assessments of urban environments can be completed considering all road users in a single platform.

PTV Vissim is rounded off with comprehensive analysis options, creating a powerful tool for the evaluation and planning of urban and extra-urban transport infrastructure. For example, the simulation software may be used to create detailed computational results or impressive 3D animations for different scenarios. It is the perfect way to present convincing and comprehensible planned infrastructure measures to decision-makers and the public.”⁶

Details of the operation of PTV Vissim can be found at (Fellendorf, et.al., 2011).

“The Emission Model DLL allows vehicle emissions to be calculated with a user-defined algorithm written in C/C++. Vehicle specific information is passed from Vissim to the DLL, which then computes the emissions and returns the results back to Vissim⁷.”

In the simulations carried out within the scope of RECIPROCITY, we integrated emission computation algorithms published and widely accepted regarding Diesel cars⁸.

Sources:

- (Zephaniah, 2016)
- (Jo, Kim, 2021)⁹.
- For e-cars and e-bikes, we have used the emission model recently published in (Weiss, et.al., 2020).

To overcome the need for integrating user-defined algorithms to Vissim for emission calculation directly from the tool itself, recently, PTV has incorporated the Bosch Emission Model into Vissim. This facility may be explored as a viable alternative to selecting and using different vehicle models¹⁰.

⁴ <https://www.ptvgroup.com/en/solutions/products/ptv-vissim/>

⁵ <https://www.ptvgroup.com/en/solutions/products/ptv-vissim/>

⁶ <https://civitas.eu/tool-inventory/ptv-vissim>

⁷ <https://company.ptvgroup.com/en-us/emission-modeling-with-an-external-model-dll-in-vissim>

⁸ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/highlights/average-co2-emissions-from-new-cars-vans-2019>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13179761>

¹⁰ <https://company.ptvgroup.com/en/ptv-vissim-emissions-calculation-from-bosch>

4. Simulation Results

4.1. Intelligent BRT (Istanbul, TR)

In this section, impacts of the driver-based traditional and platooning operation of BRT as well as autonomous operation with platooning will be presented, based on PTV Vissim simulation. 3900 seconds of operation was simulated, with the first 300 seconds discarded as warm-up period, or transient. Thus, the impacts of one-hour operation of the BRT are reported in Table 11 for the line 34Z (Zincirlikuyu – Söğütluçeşme) and in Table 12 for the line 34 (Avcılar – Zincirlikuyu).

In these simulations, CO₂ emissions of busses are calculated by the PTV Vissim simulator according to the PHEM (Passenger car and Heavy duty vehicle Emissions Model) (Hausberger, et.al., 2003) based on intensive measurements on heavy vehicles' engine test beds.

While this model caters for a variety of vehicle and engine types, in the present simulations, only Euro III diesel fuel has been considered.

Table 11 34Z Zincirlikuyu – Söğütluçeşme Line

Scenario	Σ Passenger	Avg. Waiting in Station	Avg. Speed	Avg. Travel Distance (m)	Avg. Travel Time (sec)	Avg. Passenger Wait+Travel Time	Σ Fuel Consumption (gr)	Fuel Cons. Per Km	Σ CO2 Emissions (gr)	CO2 Emissions Per Km.
		(sec)	(km/h)			(sec)		(gr/Km)		(gr/km)
B1	19.764	187,44	48,16	1280,74	95,74	283,18	3,74	4786,70	637.587,80	497,83
B2	17.491	199,15	47,69	1326,05	100,10	299,25	3,77	5004,69	666.624,80	502,71
A1	17.503	174,51	48,65	1346,74	99,66	274,17	3,70	4982,94	663.727,20	492,84
A2	17.751	217,01	58,87	1596,95	97,66	314,67	3,06	4883,05	650.422,00	407,29
A3	17.446	211,42	59,09	1596,57	97,27	308,69	3,05	4863,53	647.822,60	405,76
A4	17.502	170,93	48,79	1346,01	99,32	270,25	3,69	4965,81	661.445,80	491,41
A5	17.681	174,14	60,96	1628,24	96,16	270,30	2,95	4807,52	640.361,80	393,28

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Table 12 34 Avçılar – Zincirlikuyu Line

Scenario	Σ Passengers	Avg. Wait in Station	Avg. Speed	Avg. Travel Distance (m)	Avg. Travel Time (sec)	Avg. Passenger Wait+Travel Time	Σ Fuel Consumption (gr)	Fuel Cons. Per Km	Σ CO2 Emissions (gr)	CO2 Emissions Per Km.
		(sec)	(km/h)			(sec)		(gr/Km)		(gr/km)
B1	31.748	633,93	31,47	3181,25	363,92	997,85	18.196,38	5,72	2.423.757,42	761,89
B2	34.968	445,26	34,17	3599,09	379,18	824,44	18.960,43	5,27	2.525.528,88	701,71
A1	35.195	392,17	35,33	3705,7	377,60	769,77	18.882,44	5,10	2.515.140,88	678,72
A2	35.288	505,24	38,15	3919,15	369,83	875,07	18.490,25	4,72	2.462.901,57	628,43
A3	35.331	500,05	38,23	3914,75	368,64	868,69	18.429,79	4,71	2.454.848,43	627,08
A4	35.188	389,13	35,39	3701,45	376,53	765,66	18.825,91	5,07	2.507.611,35	677,47
A5	35.564	420,26	40,28	4054,27	362,35	782,61	18.118,31	4,47	2.413.359,16	595,26

The first observation on these assessments is that driverless/autonomous platooning consistently reduces CO₂ emissions per kilometer. Depending on the route characteristics, reduction of CO₂ emission may be up to 21% - viz. Last column of Table 8, difference between B1 – base single bus operation by driver and A5, autonomous platooning at a target speed of 90 km/h and fast deceleration. In the shorter Zincirlikuyu – Söğütlüçeşme line (Table 9), the difference of emission per-km between driver based platooning at 10 sec inter-bus departure time and autonomous platooning is, again, 21,8%.

Autonomous platooning is seen to reduce average total waiting and travel times, as well, on both routes. In the longer line 34, the reduction is 21,5%, from 998 sec to 783 sec. In the shorter and less loaded line, 34Z, the reduction is not as significant, from 299 sec to 270 sec, merely 9,6%. While the travel times are not significantly different, the times spent by passengers waiting in stations are noticeably reduced, by 13 sec (7%) in the short line and by 114 sec (18%) in the long line.

As expected, platooning with lower inter-departure times (3 sec, scenarios A1 and A2) also helps in reducing the time spent by passengers at stations.

4.2. Softly Mobile Tourism Mobility (Werfenweng, AT)

For the topology given in Section 3.2 and the configurations defined in Section 3.2.1, simulations were run for a single 12 hour day. Data for the first 10 minutes was discarded as a warm-up period. That is, the operation and data collection lasts for 43200 seconds.

The first scenario is the shuttle-only case, that is no e-bikes and no e-cars to respond to the passenger demand. The average waiting times of passengers and total fuel consumption and aggregate screen house gas and particle emissions for this scenario are given in Table 11 for different frequencies of shuttle service.

Table 15 Diesel shuttle-only scenario (total: 698 passengers)

N trips per day	Avr waiting time (min)	Total fuel consumption (kg)	Total emission (g CO2)
144	3,8	7315	4389
72	7,9	3652	2191
48	12,2	2430	1458
32	18,3	1611	967
24	25,8	1201	721

The second scenario considers sharing the daily passenger demand between shuttles and rented e-cars (Table 14). In e-cars, the number of passengers were varying stochastically between 1 and 4.

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Table 14 Daily passenger demand shared between shuttles and rented e-cars (total: 712 passengers)

N shuttle trips	N e-car trips	Avrg waiting time (min)	Diesel fuel consumption (kg)	E consumption (kWh)	Diesel emission (g CO2)	E- Indirect emission (g CO2)	Total CO2 (g)
72	12	5	3696	43,8	2150	560	13404
72	16	4,2	3703	57,1	2137	8160	18457
48	16	3,7	2388	55	1397	8762	18741
48	24	3,3	2415	77,9	1460	13161	27781
32	24	5,5	1703	83,7	982	13012	27007
32	36	3,7	1680	124,8	951	18694	38338
24	36	4,6	1265	120,9	735	19003	38741
24	48	3,7	1281	171,4	742	25857	52456

The third and last scenario studied in this demonstration was sharing the passenger load among shuttle, e-cars and e-bikes.

Considering that currently there are 20 e-bikes and 11 e-cars available for rental, it was assumed that e-bike rentals would be on a per-day basis. That is, not more than a single person would use an e-bike per day, and at most four trips per day per person would be made by e-bike. The number of daily shuttle trips were varied as 24, 48 and 72 trips per day. The number of total e-car trips per day were taken as 12, 24 and 36. The number of passengers in e-cars was assumed to vary stochastically between 1 and 4, like scenario 2.

In Table 15, maximum use of e-cars and maximum use of e-bikes are emphasized in green and light green, respectively.

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Table 15 Daily passenger demand shared among shuttle, e-cars and e-bikes (total: 731 passengers)

Number of shuttle trips/day	Number of e-car trips/day	Number of e-bike trips/day	Average waiting time for shuttle (min)	Total diesel fuel cons. (kg)	Total e-car energy cons. (kWh)	Total e-bike energy cons. (kWh)	Total diesel emissions (g CO2)	Total indirect e-emissions (g CO2)
24	12	40	8,6	1273	41,6	2,7	729	7416
24	24	40	6,5	1260	86,0	2,9	730	14016
24	36	20	6,1	1265	113,5	1,4	742	20208
48	12	40	3,1	2379	44,9	2,9	1373	7416
48	24	40	2,9	2421	90,1	2,9	1496	14016
48	24	20	3,1	2406	87,6	1,6	1502	13608
48	36	40	2,8	2412	127,7	3,1	1480	20616
48	36	20	2,6	2399	121,9	1,5	1487	20208
72	12	40	3,3	3695	47,2	2,8	2146	7416
72	12	20	3,1	3681	46,0	1,6	2130	7008
72	24	40	2,7	3730	83,3	3,0	2137	14016
72	24	20	2,9	3690	89,4	1,6	2166	13608
72	36	40	2,5	3704	130,0	2,9	2160	20616
72	36	20	2,6	3712	128,2	1,6	2120	20208

Upon comparing Tables 13, 14 and 15, the first observation is that indirect emissions from electric vehicles are not negligible at all. However, if considered at a local scale, only the emissions from the Diesel shuttles remain as effective, clearly showing the impact of e-vehicles in the direction of clean mobility. At a global scale, however, the effects of producing electrical energy become significant, and the only way towards clean energy at a global scale would be the use of renewable sources like solar, wind or hydroelectric energy generation.

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Furthermore, as there is no waiting for rented e-cars and e-bikes, average waiting times, calculated by adding all time spent by passengers waiting for shuttle service and dividing the sum by the total number of passengers, average waiting times are drastically reduced. Thus e-bikes and e-cars are seen to be clearly beneficial at the local scale for clean and smart mobility.

The two cells framed in green indicate the scenario in which the minimum CO₂ emission is observed, when all 731 passengers throughout the day are served by the lowest number of services of the Diesel shuttle, and only 12 or 24 e-car trips, while the number of bike trips in the day under consideration is the highest, at 40.

5. Conclusion

In this report, the work done to prepare the use case definitions and the methodology for selecting use cases to be proposed for replication in follower cities, referred as Mapping and Impact Assessment (T 1.4), in short, have been presented.

After the Master Mobility Workshop and the Local Mobility Workshops, as well as the interviews carried out with all identified stakeholders within the scope of T 1.3, the set of use cases described in one-page leaflets (see Annex 1) have been obtained from partners and stakeholders.

Expected impacts of replicating these use cases as assessed by Project partners will be presented to Mobility Task Force (MTF) members as well as interested stakeholders within the scope of the Replication Roadmap Definition Workshops (RRDW) to be realized within the scope of Task T1.5.

The simulation-based impact assessment study has illustrated the applicability of the tool utilized for this purpose, to the use cases to be finally selected within the RRDW's in T 1.5.

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Annex

By clicking on this link, it will be possible to review the database of use-cases collected throughout the process discussed in the document and to have a look at the process implemented in the project team in order to deal with these cases. As the use-cases are at the core of the T.1.5 work, the full use-cases will be presented later in the project.

The document should be read as indicated below

Column name & letter	Meaning
A – Use-case number	Used for internal purpose – no specific meaning
B – Use-case short name	Used for internal purpose and for writing the one-pagers that will be shared in the replication workshops
C – Responsible RCP partner	Partner who identified the use-cases
D – Use-case was identified during...	RECIPROCITY activity during which the use-case was identified
E – Use-case refers to which category	Category used within the RECIPROCITY project
F - Technology readiness levels (TRL)	As declared by the RCP partners
G - Simplicity to replicate use case	As declared by the RCP partner

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RECIPROCITY (Replication of innovative concepts for peri-urban, rural or inner-city mobility), coordinated by R-Tech Regensburg (Germany), involves 10 partners including clusters, regional development agencies, innovation accelerators and universities. The project started in February 2021 and will run for 32 months.

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